

" Peace is maintained by the equilibrium of the forces (military, economic, social etc) and will continue as long as this equilibrium exists, and no longer."

Carl von Clausewitz, *On War*

Throughout the history of the known world, man has never been so worried about the events and the happenings which determine the future of himself; the events and crises which no one has ever experienced before. The Russian invasion of Ukraine has launched another fresh political and philosophical debate among the intellectuals to discuss and define the final outcome of the conflict. Whether the Russian attempt of annexation was a part of Balance of Threat Theory or a prisoner's dilemma, history seems to repeat itself. After the decades long intermission, the world has become multipolar and this polarization is stocking the drums of a big war or maybe a big final war. The shift of the center of power from west to east and the construction of new alliances are depicting the picture of the world before the Great War.

Is peace only an illusion? Should we accept and admit that, as Thomas Hobbes concluded, we are in a perpetual state of war or a war of all against all? The following essay comprehensively renders the picture of a conflicting world in a philosophical manner.

On the eve of the new year, former Russian president Dmitry Medvedev shared a number of predictions about the downfall of the west's monopoly on world affairs and the conflicts in central Europe. Medvedev, who holds a doctorate degree in law and served as the president of the Russian Federation from 2008 to 2012 and Prime Minister from 2012 to 2020 is currently serving as the Deputy Chairman of the Security Council of the Russian Federation. Medvedev's 27 December predictions are as below.

1. Oil prices will rise to \$150 a barrel and gas prices will top \$5 per 1 cubic meters.
2. UK will join the European Union.
3. The European Union will collapse after UK's return.
4. Poland and Hungary will occupy the western regions of the Ukraine.
5. The Fourth Reich will be created in the territories of Germany and its neighbours including Poland, Baltic States, Czech Republic, Slovakia, Kiev Republic and other outcasts.
6. War will broke out between France and the Fourth Reich and Europe will be divided.
7. Northern Ireland will separate from UK and join the Republic of Ireland.
8. Civil War will break out in USA. California and Texas will become independent. Texas and Mexico will form an allied state. Elon Musk will win the elections and become the President of America.
9. All stock markets and financial institutions will leave the USA and Europe and move to Asia.
10. The Bretton Woods System will collapse leading the IMF and the World Bank to crash. Euro and Dollar will stop circulating as global reserve currencies. Digital currencies will be used.

Medvedev's prophecies might be a politician's personal assumptions or a pipe dream and being a top supporter of Putin's War, one can ignore him thinking that he is not the first Russian to

declare such absurd guesses. However, there are some deep phrases in his predictions which are likely to happen as there are a number of supportive facts in favour of his sentiments.

The non-renewable energy sources are not enough for the new world . Each day, the demand for oil is increasing while the supply is decreasing. Global liquid energy demand increased by 0.9 MMb/d (million barrels per day) in November 2022 to 100.2 MMb/d due to an increased demand from China. We have seen the 1973 OPEC oil embargo which caused an immense hike of oil prices. In any case, whether the oil production is slumped by natural causes or by oil producing countries, the prices will increase as mentioned by Medvedev.

After Brexit and withdrawal from the EU, most of the people of the United Kingdom want to rejoin the EU. Many UK parliamentarians also have supported the idea to rejoin the union because it is more favourable for UK. On the other hand, the question of the collapse of the EU is also acceptable. Diversity in ethnicity and cultural difference is one of the problems of the union. The Schengen Agreement is the probable cause of the future collapse of the EU. While the agreement allows the citizens to freely move in all member countries, the illegal immigration and flow of people from poor countries to the big economic powers such as Germany is the main issue. Moreover, nationalism is again in rise in Europe.

After the end of World War 2 in Europe, many countries shifted towards political and economic union and the next 50 years saw a peaceful and rapid growth in economy and there was peace and stability. However, the political waves are shifting and Europe is on the line of fire . A new period of populism and nationalism is emerging in Europe.

When Donald Trump won the 2016 presidential elections, " America First " was his slogan. Trump's election campaign was against some Muslims and Mexicans and his efforts to limit immigration and trade barriers was seen as a sign of ethnic Nationalism. Trump's victory was celebrated in most of the powerful Europe during the elections and portrayed Trump as a Nationalist.

Marine Le Pen, French National Front party leader expressed antiglobalization and anti-immigration policies. Marine has promised to take back France by withdrawing from the European Union. Trump appreciated this move, as he did when Britain voted last year to leave the EU after Brexit.

This is not a single example. Geert Wilders, founder of the Dutch Party for Freedom, and Nigel Farage, leader of the United Kingdom Independence Party, which struggled for Britain's withdrawal from the European Union and Matteo Salvini, leader of Italy's Northern League all have similar ideas.

The occupation of western Ukraine by Poland and Hungary is not a big thing. If Russia succeeds in occupying Ukrainian territories, Poland and Hungary can also annex parts of the western Ukraine. However, Medvedev's statement might be a political statement as Russia has always accused Poland of its intentions to annex parts of western Ukraine.

The Rise of Fourth Reich and the future Franco-German War is the most captivating thing. Days ago, in early December 2022, German law enforcement agencies arrested a few dozen suspects who were staging a coup. These suspects who were members of the Reichsbuerger or Imperial Citizens movement believe that today's German state doesn't exist and it's created by the Allies of the Second World War, hence having a belief of Imperial German State. Adolf

Hitler's following statement should be kept in mind which he wrote in his famous book *Mein Kampf*:

" We National Socialists have purposely drawn a line through the line of conduct followed by pre-war Germany in foreign policy. We put an end to the perpetual Germanic march towards the South and West of Europe and turn our eyes towards the lands of the East. But when we speak of new territory in Europe today, we must principally think of Russia and the border states subject to her."

(Adolf Hitler, *Mein Kampf*)

If someone thinks that Germans have totally forgotten Hitler's ideas then it is a great illusion. When a crisis appears or someone becomes too much powerful then extremism comes forward. Hitler's ideas of expansion, called in German as *Lebensraum*, will be again in the political talks. It's only the NATO, or broadly saying, American presence in Europe that Europe is somehow in union. Whenever the European Union ended and the states withdrew from the economic and military alliance, an era of wars will erupt again. The old Franco-German rivalry will be revived in case Germany withdrew from the Union. The quest for territory will be the next world problem. Germany has the largest economy in the European Union and will have a deep effect on future European politics.

The Troubles or the Northern Ireland Conflict which started in 1968 lasted until 1998. The conflict was between Protestant Unionists who were in favour to remain part of UK and the Roman Catholic Nationalists who protested for being a part of the Irish Republic. Although the Good Friday Agreement of 1998 officially ended the conflict however, the situation may erupt at any time. All of these events signal that Nationalism and ethnicity are once again rising in Europe.

Medvedev's prediction about a possible civil war in the USA is a dead notion. For a few decades, at least, we can't expect any such thing in the USA. However, Trump's re-election can boost this possibility as he ethnic Nationalism ideology as described earlier.

As mentioned above, the world center of power is shifting from west to east. The polarity of international anarchic politics will not accept a single currency. As mentioned by Henry Kissinger, the 21st Century World will contain six major powers - United States, Europe, China, Japan, Russia and India. The four major powers are Asian and the changing picture of Middle Eastern Muslim countries is changing the geopolitics. America has taken the most benefit from the Bretton Woods System of 1944 which controlled the whole world till this day. With the rise of power in the Eastern flank, the significance of monetary institutions such as the IMF and World Bank would crumble.

Since the end of the Cold War in 1989 to 2000, 111 armed conflicts have occurred in 74 different locations around the world. Seven were Interstate wars while nine were Intrastate Wars with foreign intervention. Hence, whether it is the case of ancient Greece where Spartan's fear of Athenian superiority caused the war or the modern world, the alliances of the previous century and the struggle for colonization, the ethnic Nationalism and security concerns of the 21st century, the world is in a perpetual state of War. Medvedev's predictions seems a wise man's prophecies which should never be ignored.

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